

IR0000014 – Itserr

Data-Acquisition Procedures

Document reference:	ITSERR-D10.3-[DAP]	
Version number:	01.00	
Status:	FINAL	
Last revision date:	26/01/2026	by: Andrea D'Andrea, Gilda Ferrandino, Alexia Pavan
Verification date:	02/02/2026	by: Luisa Sernicola
Approval date:	DD/MM/YYYY	by: MUR
Subject:	IR0000014 – ITSERR Data-Acquisition Procedures	
Filename:	ITSERR_D10.3_01.00_Draft.docx	

This document is available in the ITSERR WP Management document repository at:
ITSERR-WP10\Deliverables\D10.3_\DAP

Associated project to RESILIENCE

Change history

Version Number	Date	Status	Summary of main or important changes
00.01	25/11/2025	WORKING	Working version
00.02	26/01/2026	DRAFT	Complete revision of the document after ITSERR Board review
01.00	04/02/2026	FINAL	Finalisation

Distribution List

Name	Company	Role
ITSERR Board Members	All ITSERR partners	

Table of Contents

Document overview	5
Objectives	5
Dataset and Preliminary Data Model	5
The use of technologies	16
Digital 3D methods applied to cultural heritage	18
Digitising Cultural Heritage and the Creation of 3D Models: Methods and Challenges	21
Photogrammetry	21
Meroitic stele as a case study	24
Laser scanner	27
Reflectance Transformation Imaging (RTI) and Virtual RTI	29
The magic-therapeutic bowls as a case study	33
Digital Acquisition Methods	34
From Model to Matter: The Role of Archaeometry in Artefact Interpretation	37
Characterization of Artefacts	37
Contribution for Conservation.....	38
Chronological Frameworks and Dating Methods	38
Analytical Techniques and Applications	38
Analytical Instruments within ITSERR Project	40
Beyond the Model: Archaeometric Investigations of Magic-Therapeutic Bowls. A Potential Case Study	42
References	44
Selected Web Resources	46
1 Annexes	47

List of Tables

Table 1 Mapping of TEI/Epidoc to Cidoc-CRM for the description of physical object	10
Table 2 Mapping of TEI/Epidoc to Cidoc-CRM for the description of the iconography.....	12
Table 3 Mapping of TEI/Epidoc to CRMtex for the description of the text	13
Table 4 Characteristics of the Acquired Photographs.....	34

Associated project to RESILIENCE

List of Figures

Figure 1 ICCD RA cataloguing record of a magic bowl (MO1156).....	7
Figure 2 Graph of CIDOC-CRM. The description of Physical Object	11
Figure 3 Graph of Cidoc-CRM. The iconography.....	11
Figure 4 Graph of Cidoc-CRM. The text.....	14
Figure 5 Graph of Cidoc-CRM. The archaeological context and interpretation	15
Figure 6 Recto and Verso of the stele of Amanishakheto (I BC – IAD).....	25
Figure 7 Photogrammetric processing	26
Figure 8 Recto and verso views of the 3D-printed stele	26
Figure 9 MO1152, Point cloud generated after image alignment	35
Figure 10 MO1152, placement of control points on the point cloud.....	36

Document overview

Objectives

This deliverable has a dual objective: to validate the preliminary data model and to indicate procedures for the digitization of texts and manuscripts, enriching the digitization process with 3D data or with information derived from archaeometric analyses.

D10.2 identified the prevailing data models in the religious studies community and outlined a framework that supports Open Science principles and broader research objectives. Building on D10.2, which provided guidelines for data providers and researchers to produce standardized data and suggested pathways for integrating different datasets, this deliverable focuses on the methods for ensuring data readability and reuse, emphasizing the adoption of standardized systems.

The dataset examined in WP10 is inherently heterogeneous, comprising data from different research fields - such as philological studies of manuscripts spanning different cultures and periods, and archaeological investigations of religious artefacts in various contexts - all united by their common focus on the religious aspect. This disciplinary diversity represents a significant challenge: different academic traditions employ distinct descriptive frameworks, terminologies, and classification systems. Moreover, as demonstrated in the previous D10.2 and in a related article (D'Andrea A., Ferrandino G. 2025), the concept of "religious" does not have the same meaning or value across different cultures and historical periods, adding a further layer of complexity to the goal of proper semantic data integration. Within a platform designed to aggregate datasets related to religious studies, such heterogeneity introduces a complexity that must be addressed to ensure data discovery and reusability. A key issue, for example, is the definition of chronological periods of archaeological objects, whose classification varies depending on the culture that produced them and the study traditions that have identified them. Therefore, D10.3 proposes methods for structuring and integrating datasets formalized in different systems and for documenting the knowledge path that leads to the interpretation of objects, highlighting, above all, the centrality of context in the reconstruction process.

The second objective of D10.3, no less fundamental, consists in the need to provide users with limited digital skills the competencies to be able to digitize and analyze objects of magical-religious content using different acquisition technologies and digital information processing

Dataset and Preliminary Data Model

RETINA collects data from multiple sources, each documented according to different descriptive standards and methodologies. The collection includes:

- manuscripts encoded in TEI/XML format, which provides detailed philological and codicological annotations;
- archaeological objects from collections preserved in the museum of the University of Naples L'Orientale described using the ICCD (Istituto Centrale per il Catalogo e la Documentazione) standard cataloging system, which ensures compliance with national methodological principles and terminological tools;
- archaeological data from field missions, documented through customized Excel spreadsheets developed by scholars to meet specific research needs.

This multi-format composition reflects the diversified nature of cultural heritage documentation, classification, and study practices. While the use of TEI/XML represents a well-established international standard, particularly widespread for manuscript description and archiving, regarding archaeological finds that bear inscriptions, greater heterogeneity is observed in the choice of descriptive systems; this variety stems from the need to describe both the archaeological object and the text inscribed on it.

Even in the field of manuscripts, the description of the physical object is fundamental, but this need is only partially met by TEI/XML, which allows the inclusion of information about the material support. In the case of archaeological objects, the interpretation of the nature and function of the artefact depends not only on physical characteristics and the presence of any symbolic or iconographic representations, but also on the archaeological context of the object's use. Often, the inscription on the artefact is brief, although closely connected to a ritual function.

In the survey described in D10.1, in many archives priority is given to the description of the object, with reference to the archaeological context and, only to a lesser extent, to the analysis and interpretation of the text. With few exceptions, the text itself is not optimally described. There are also digital archives that focus specifically on inscriptions, such as DASI¹ (Digital Archive for the Study of Pre-Islamic Arabian Inscriptions) or ItAnt² (Languages and Cultures of Ancient Italy: Historical Linguistics and Digital Models); both use TEI/EpiDoc for text description.

In our dataset, objects from museum collections are described according to the standard cataloging system established by ICCD, which provides a set of codified methodological principles and specific tools to implement cataloging according to homogeneous criteria at the Italian national level.

¹ <https://dasi.cnr.it>

² <https://www.ilc.cnr.it/progetti/itant/>

CODICI (CD)	
Tipo scheda (TSK)	RA
Livello ricerca (LIR)	C
<i>CODICE UNIVOCO (NCT)</i>	
Codice regione (NCTR)	15
Numero catalogo generale (NCTN)	00000264
Ente schedatore (ESC)	UNIOR
Ente competente (ECP)	UNIOR
Ente proponente (EPR)	UNIOR
RELAZIONI (RV)	
<i>STRUTTURA COMPLESSA (RVE)</i>	
Livello (RVEL)	0
<i>RELAZIONI DIRETTE (RSE)</i>	
Tipo Relazione (RSER)	luogo di esposizione
Tipo scheda (RSET)	A
Codice bene (RSEC)	630570

Figure 1 ICCD RA cataloguing record of a magic bowl (M01156)

This system is based on structured descriptive models (records), terminological tools, and shared methodologies. The components interact with each other, creating a true "knowledge system" that facilitates interoperability and data exchange processes. The system codified by ICCD describes the object as an administrative, physical, and linguistic object. However, it is not used outside of Italy.

To promote the sharing of Italian cultural heritage data with other information systems, ICCD has developed several mappings that allow its records to be transformed into international standard formats. Records can be exported to Dublin Core through the OAI-PMH protocol³. The ArCo project⁴ has converted the entire General Catalog into RDF-based Linked Open Data. Furthermore, a mapping to CIDOC-CRM has been developed that enables semantic integration with other cultural heritage information systems worldwide⁵. What matters is the possibility offered to any type of user to search records in archives, obtain information, and reuse such data.

In addition to data structured according to ICCD, WP₁₀ has also examined archives from the archaeological missions of the University of Naples L'Orientale. These archives, structured in spreadsheets used for resource description, document both digital and physical objects, with particular attention to the cataloging of the objects themselves and their discovery context.

³ Here an example of the mapping: <http://www.iccd.beniculturali.it/getFile.php?id=1170>

⁴ <https://iccd.beniculturali.it/it/percondividere/ProgettoArCo>

⁵ Felicetti, A., et al. 2013

Associated project to RESILIENCE

The archive examined for the project presented significant challenges related to standardization, data consistency, and metadata management. These difficulties arise from the variety of formats, media, and conventions adopted over the years by the different teams that have succeeded one another in the research. The dataset includes digital resources, paper materials, and GIS documents, creating a complex and fragmented structure that encompasses both analog and digital formats. To address and manage such complexity and ensure interoperability, traceability, and compliance with FAIR principles, comprehensive procedures for digitization, cataloging, and data encoding were necessary. This made it necessary to examine and analyze the entire corpus of materials, organize them according to uniform typologies and criteria, and assign a unique identifier (ID) to each source. From the archive, some objects considered interesting for ITSERR purposes were selected. Each artefact is documented through multiple information sources, including photographs, field diaries, and catalog cards. These resources describe the same object, offering different formats, digitization processes, and, above all, different perspectives, all complementary for proper identification and interpretation of the object and its discovery context.

Given the diversity of approaches present in the dataset - composed of data described with TEI/XML, ICCD metadata, and customized systems created by scholars without reference to standardization frameworks - ensuring data interoperability is essential to enable interdisciplinary research. This requires alignment with shared standards that facilitate both digital preservation and information reuse.

D10.2 identified these challenges and described the main standards used in different research communities, recognizing however that no single approach could satisfy all the disciplinary needs examined. However, the survey conducted on various digital archives containing texts and objects from the Nile Valley and beyond revealed the particular versatility of CIDOC-CRM as a binding agent due to its characteristic as a standard capable of capturing the complexity of information.

CIDOC-CRM, including its extensions, appears to be the most valid tool for mapping the different approaches and objectives of a heterogeneous archive, emphasizing the relevant aspects of magical-religious indicators documented by objects and texts. Many scholars have recently produced mappings of their datasets to CIDOC-CRM, recognizing how this ontology is capable of addressing the real complexity of analysis and treatment of cultural heritage documentation. In the case of religious objects and texts, CIDOC-CRM can represent the entire life cycle of objects, which includes not only production, use, and circulation in antiquity, but also modern musealization and restoration.

The possibility of extending the model, with less general ontologies more connected to the specific task, allows us to represent all the information potentially conveyed by an archaeological object, such as the text and discovery context, offering the possibility to reconstruct and represent the flow of the entire archaeological interpretation. As noted in

D10.2, identifying the semantic field of an artefact belonging to a culture distant in time and space is complicated and requires rigorous study of multiple factors, especially in the case of archaeological artefacts of everyday use. Following Renfrew's words: "The archaeologist cannot observe beliefs: one can only work with material remains, the consequences of actions. In favorable cases these remains are the result of actions that we can plausibly interpret as deriving from religious faith," we can highlight the need to critically place archaeological interpretation in its proper context, maintaining complete and high-quality documentation capable of recording the entire interpretive process itself. Simply applying a label to an object, placing it in a specific category created by a scholar, is not sufficient to describe all its informative power; indeed, this process can prove reductive, obscuring intangible and nuanced relationships and, above all, obscuring contextual information essential for correct interpretation of the object.

Considering that many digital archives adopt TEI/EpiDoc XML for the description of texts and inscriptions, CIDOC-CRM can serve as a bridge between textual encoding standards and semantic modeling, facilitating interoperability between textual data and material culture objects, allowing textual and epigraphic content to be linked to archaeological contexts, provenance information, and related artefacts. A model that captures the complexity of artefacts and their meaning offers a comprehensive descriptive framework, constituting a valuable tool not only for understanding the data, but also for its very preservation. Furthermore, CIDOC-CRM can be easily mapped to other widely adopted standards such as EDM (Europeana Data Model) used by Europeana and Schema.org, ensuring compatibility between different digital ecosystems.

Following such an approach, CIDOC-CRM classes and properties and its extensions were selected to formalize and represent the objects included in the collections considered by WP10. This section explains the process of identifying CIDOC-CRM classes useful for describing WP10 datasets. From the FAIRness perspective, this work reuses the path already traced by other projects such as EAGLE⁶ and ItAnt⁷.

The following sections describe the mapping process, organized into three main components: (I) archaeological artefacts as physical objects, (II) inscribed texts and their linguistic features, and (III) archaeological context and interpretive processes.

I. The first step consists in the description of the archaeological object as E22 Man_Made_Object.

1. The classes and properties used to represent the object map the tags in the <support> node in the TEI/EpiDoc XML file (for the TEI/EpiDoc XML see the Annex, lines 45-62).
- 2.

⁶ <https://www.eagle-network.eu/>

⁷ Murano F, Felicetti A., 2023

In TEI/EpiDoc the object is considered a support and its description is grouped in the <msDesc> node

Table 1 Mapping of TEI/Epidoc to Cidoc-CRM for the description of physical object

TEI/EpiDoc	Path	CIDOC-CRM Entity	CIDOC-CRM Property
<support>	physDesc/supportDesc/support	E22 Man-made Object	
<objectType>	//support/objectType	E55 Type	P2 has type
<material>	//support/material	E57 Material	P45 consists of
<dimension>	//support/dimension	E54 Dimension	P43 has dimension
<height>	//support/dimension/height	E55 Type	P2 has type
<width>	//support/dimension/width	E55 Type	P2 has type
<depth>	//support/dimension/depth	E55 Type	P2 has type
<rs>	//support/rs	E11 Modification	P31 has modified
<condition>	//support/condition	E3 Condition State	P44 has condition
<note>	//support/condition/note	E62 String	P3 has note

Attributes TEI/EpiDoc	Path	CIDOC-CRM Entity	CIDOC-CRM Property
@ana	<objectType ana=[URI]>	URI GETTY AAT	P2 has type
@ana	<material ana=[URI]>	URI GETTY AAT	P2 has type
@unit	<dimensions unit="cm">	E58 Measurement Unit	P91 has unit
@quantity	<height quantity="">	xsd:decimal, xsd:integer, xsd:float	P90 has value

The description of the object is connected to the description of images, decoration and texts that it may support.

Figure 2 Graph of CIDOC-CRM. The description of Physical Object

2. Classes and properties were subsequently selected to represent the iconography.

Figure 3 Graph of CIDOC-CRM. The iconography

TEI/EpiDoc XML provides a dedicated structure for describing decorations or iconography on the support or accompanying the text (see the Annex, lines 63-91). Iconographic features are documented using the <decoDesc> element, while the <term ana=""> element allows the insertion of URIs that link controlled vocabularies.

While in TEI/EpiDoc the subjects represented in a scene are typically described in textual form within elements such as <decoNote> or <p>, CIDOC-CRM provides the means to formalize these contents through structured conceptual categories, making the implicit knowledge explicit and machine-readable.

In CIDOC-CRM, a scene is modeled as an instance of class E36 Visual_Item, and the iconographic subjects it represents are connected through the property P138 represents. This property links the visual representation to specific concepts, typically classified as instances of E55 Type or other relevant CIDOC-CRM entities, allowing a precise semantic description of the iconographic content.

What in TEI/EpiDoc remains a generic and unstructured description, in CIDOC-CRM transforms into explicit semantic relationships and formalized conceptual categories, facilitating interoperability and semantic queries on iconographic content.

Table 2 Mapping of TEI/Epidoc to Cidoc-CRM for the description of the iconography

TEI/EpiDoc	Path	CIDOC-CRM Entity	CIDOC-CRM Property
<decoNote>	//physDesc/decodes/decoNote	E36 Visual Item	P128 carries
@type	//decoNote/term type= ""	E55 Type	P2 has Type
@ref	//decoNote/term type= "" ref= "URI">	E52 Identifier	P1 is identified by
@term	//decoNote/term persName= "">	E39 Actor	P138 represents

In the archive examined by WP10, iconography is represented by figures engraved on the support, symbols, and objects such as amulets in the shape of some figures. All these categories can be described in generic form descriptively in TEI/EpiDoc, while CIDOC-CRM defines different structures. In the case of a scene, the E36 Visual Item could be linked to an E5 Event which is the activity represented in the scene that has actors and place. Otherwise, the object in the form of an animal-like figure in the amulet can be defined as a E55 Type and is a property of the object itself. The definition of the subject of an image can be expressed through the use of Iconclass⁸, a standard system for classifying image content.

⁸ <https://iconclass.org/>

II. Another relevant aspect is the text. The proposed data model responds to research needs by treating inscribed objects and their texts as separate but interconnected entities. Often archaeological and epigraphic archives show predictable patterns of emphasis that lead to incomplete documentation. On one hand, object-centered archives tend to treat texts as secondary features, providing only superficial mentions of inscriptions without recording paleographic details, linguistic content, or textual variants. The text becomes simply an attribute of the material artefact rather than an entity carrying information useful for detailed analysis. On the other hand, text-centered archives reduce the physical object to its role as a carrier or support, neglecting the crucial archaeological context, material properties, production techniques, or depositional history that could influence textual interpretation. In this way, the complexity of inscribed objects as simultaneous material and textual phenomena is not captured. The separation thus highlighted can be reconciled through a CIDOC-CRM based model, which for text description uses the CRMtex extension.

The CRMtex extension leverages existing standards: textual data encoded in TEI/EpiDoc (see the Annex, lines 129-178) can be mapped to CRMtex. In the case study, the object is linked to the written text which describes the text typology, the writing system, and the language recognition process that leads to its transliteration.

Table 3 Mapping of TEI/Epidoc to CRMtex for the description of the text

TEI/EpiDoc	Path	CRMtex Entity	CRMtex Property
<layout>	//objectDesc/layout	E26 Physical Feature	
@n	//layout/n = "Recto"	E55 Type	P2 has type
@type	//layout/rs type= "execution"	E55 Type	P2 has type
@ana	//layout/rs type= "execution" ana= "URI"	E52 Identifier>URI	P1 is identified by
@source	//layout/rs type= "script" source= "URI"	E52 Identifier>URI	P1 is identified by
<note>	//layout/note	E62 String	P3 has note
<handNote>		TX10 Style	TXP has style

Associated project to RESILIENCE

<note type>	//objectDesc/handnote/note type=""	E55 Type	P2 has type
<scriptNote >	// objectDesc/scriptDesc/ scriptNote/rs type= "writing system"	TX3 Writing System	TXP1 used writing system
@subtype	//scriptDesc/scriptNote/rs subtype= "alphasyllabic"	E55 Type	P2 has type
<language>	//teiHeader/profileDesc/langUsage/languag e	E56 Language	TXP6 encodes
<text>	//TEI/text/body	TX46 Transliteration	TXP11 transcribed

Figure 4 Graph of CIDOC-CRM. The text

III. By transforming objects, texts, and their visual documentation to the status of discrete entities, the model allows each to be described in detail and contextualized within broader archaeological assemblages and stratigraphic sequences. Fundamentally, this approach provides a framework for documenting the interpretive process: reconstructive hypotheses about objects, scholarly interpretations of texts, and readings of archaeological deposits can be represented and explicitly attributed to specific researchers or research moments. These interpretations are not presented as isolated judgments, but are integrated into a comprehensive network of documented actions, events, and agents, placing individual acts of analysis in their proper historical and methodological context as components of broader research processes.

Figure 5 Graph of Cidoc-CRM. The archaeological context and interpretation

In this case, we used the CRMarchaeo module which supports the archaeological excavation process and integrates existing documentation to formalize the knowledge extracted from observations made by archaeologists. This module is closely linked to CRMsci, useful for integrating metadata on scientific observation, measurements, and processed data derived from different techniques as described in this deliverable. In our study, CRMarchaeo is also linked to CRMinf, a module designed to integrate arguments and inferences derived from archaeological reasoning, reasoning on iconographic and textual elements, and annotations in manuscripts. In the example, the analysis of the archaeological context, object, iconography, and text allows the reconstruction of activities that took place in the specific

location and the use of objects, justifying the fact that we interpret the object as part of ritual practices performed in a sacred place, such as a temple, and involving a religious authority.

The use of technologies

The digitisation of cultural heritage materials — including texts, manuscripts, and archaeological objects — plays an increasingly central role in their study, preservation, and dissemination.

While early digitisation efforts primarily focused on two-dimensional (2D) imaging, current practices increasingly adopt a more integrated and multidimensional and multimodal approach. This shift has led to a broader range of acquisition techniques and digital outputs, which vary widely depending on the type of object, the materials, and its shape and morphological features.

This report outlines the procedures commonly adopted for the digitisation of specific classes of heritage materials—namely textual artefacts and archaeological objects—with a particular focus on methods that combine visual documentation with advanced analytical data, or more precisely, metadata derived from archaeometric analyses. These data concern not only the materials used in production (what the objects are made of), but also the forms of agency behind them—that is, how they were made, by whom, and where.

Standard documentation of cultural heritage materials has traditionally relied on high-resolution photographic reproductions for inscribed objects and manuscripts, complemented by graphic representations—especially hand-drawn illustrations—for archaeological artefacts. This practice, grounded in careful and systematic observation, can reveal important details relevant to the functional and cultural interpretation of objects. Drawing, in fact, requires a trained eye and often highlights features that may go unnoticed in photographs, due to reflective surfaces, erosion, or poor state of preservation. For this reason, hand transcriptions, where they exist, must be included in the digital archive, as they complement the photographic and 3D documentation and at the same time enhance archaeological and linguistic research.

However, beyond standard documentation, the digitisation workflow presented here integrates three-dimensional (3D) data acquisition with archaeometric analyses. The inclusion of multiple data layers—visual, spatial, and, when possible, compositional—enables a more detailed understanding of both the physical properties and the historical significance of the objects. This results in enhanced digital representations that capture not only visible features but also structural, compositional, and technological attributes. Such an approach is especially valuable for archaeological objects, whose analysis relies on close examination of manufacturing techniques, use-wear patterns, working marks, and material composition. This report focuses on the digitisation of two main categories of heritage materials: textual artefacts and archaeological objects. In many cases, however, the two categories intersect:

archaeological objects may bear inscriptions, as exemplified by the magic-therapeutic bowls dataset, which combines material, iconographic and textual features.

Associated project to RESILIENCE

Particular attention is given to approaches that combine visual documentation -especially 3D representations -with metadata derived from archaeometric analyses. Such integration provides insight not only into the materials from which objects are made, but also into the processes and agents involved in their creation and use.

Building on this premise, the digitisation workflow presented here integrates three-dimensional data acquisition with archaeometric analysis.

By layering visual, spatial, and—where available—compositional data, this approach enables a more nuanced understanding of both the physical properties and the cultural biographies of the objects. The resulting digital models capture not only visible features but also structural and technological details, allowing for the close examination of manufacturing traces, use-wear patterns, and other indicators essential for archaeological interpretation.

Provenance plays a crucial role in the interpretation of certain groups of artefacts, such as the amulets from Kerma (D'Itria 2023)—one of the datasets presented by the WP—as in some cases it is precisely the contextual information that provides decisive evidence for their function. In stark contrast, the corpus of Islamic-period bowls with magical-therapeutic functions (Giunta 2018; Bernardini, Giunta 2025) is entirely devoid of information regarding specific provenance, as it consists exclusively of items acquired through the antiquities market.

The lack of contextual information presents a major obstacle, especially when it comes to identifying centres of production; nevertheless, this limitation can be partially overcome through archaeometric methods, with mineralogical and metallographic analyses playing a key role.

These scientific techniques offer an alternative investigative route, allowing researchers to analyse the mineral composition of the artefacts. This type of data can illuminate the provenance of the raw materials, shed light on the technological choices behind their production, and, in some cases, point toward possible centres of manufacture.

In the specific case of the bowls, such analyses can also clarify the nature of the substances occasionally applied to fill the incised inscriptions— an aspect that not only enhances their legibility but could also provide valuable clues about their provenance and contribute to reconstructing the “biographies” of these artefacts.

In parallel, integrating archaeometric results into digital platforms significantly enhances their research potential. Such digital enhancements contribute not only to the interpretation of individual artefacts, but also to broader processes of knowledge dissemination and collaboration.

These enriched digital objects could, in fact, improve accessibility, foster interdisciplinary collaboration, and contribute to more informed conservation strategies, while also promoting data interoperability among archaeologists, epigraphers, art historians, and conservators.

By adhering to FAIR principles—ensuring that data are Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable—these resources not only facilitate knowledge sharing across disciplinary

boundaries, but also support the long-term preservation, integration, and reuse of cultural heritage data within both research and heritage management frameworks.

The sections that follow describe the main stages of the digitisation process, the tools and techniques involved, and the criteria for data integration and management, with the aim of establishing a coherent and replicable methodology for the digital enhancement of both written and material heritage.

Digital 3D methods applied to cultural heritage

Digital 3D methods refer to the use of computer-based tools to capture and represent physical objects as digital entities within a virtual three-dimensional space. While 3D modelling is often narrowly understood as the conversion of a point cloud into a triangulated network (“mesh”) or into a textured surface, it should more accurately describe the comprehensive process which starts from data acquisition and ends with the creation of a virtual model interactively on a computer.

Digital 3D models, commonly referred to simply as 3D models, can be explored, measured, potentially annotated, and used to support cross-comparison, collaborative research, and the dissemination of knowledge. They are widely employed in multimedia museum displays, virtual reality applications, online repositories and catalogues, as well as in digital preservation efforts, deterioration simulations, object identification, and animation.

Beyond their communicative and analytical potential, 3D models also play a crucial role in the long-term preservation of cultural heritage, particularly through digital archiving. In this context, 3D modelling has become a fundamental step in safeguarding artefacts and sites. The motivations are varied: accurate documentation in case of loss or damage, support for virtual tourism and museum experiences, the development of educational resources, and the possibility of interacting with fragile objects without risk.

However, applications like digital archiving and mapping typically demand high geometric accuracy, photorealistic rendering, and detailed modelling, while also requiring cost-effectiveness, portability, and methodological flexibility.

As a result, selecting the most suitable 3D modelling technique for a given context remains a complex and critical decision (Remondino, Campana 2014).

Techniques for 3D measurement and reconstruction are generally divided into two broad categories:

- ✓ contact-based methods, such as callipers and coordinate measuring machines,
- ✓ non-contact approaches, including technologies like X-ray imaging, photogrammetry, and laser scanning.

This report focuses on non-contact methods, discussing their specific advantages and limitations.

Today, the generation of 3D models relies predominantly on non-contact systems that use light waves, through either active or passive sensors. In certain contexts, additional data sources—such as CAD models, traditional surveys, or GPS measurements—may be integrated to complement sensor-derived information. Active sensors directly capture depth data by recording the distance between the sensor and the object, producing 3D coordinates that can be used to construct a mesh. Passive sensors, on the other hand, collect images that must be processed to extract spatial information. Once acquired, the data are typically organised into a polygonal mesh, and realistic visualisation is achieved by applying photographic textures to the modelled surfaces.

Among the various 3D modelling techniques available, image-based modelling (IBM) is currently the most widely used in the field of cultural heritage. This is largely due to its relatively low cost, portability, and flexibility—it typically requires only a digital camera and suitable processing software, making it accessible even in contexts with limited technical resources. Nevertheless, IBM is just one of several approaches that can be employed, depending on the specific requirements of a project.

These approaches can be broadly grouped into four main categories:

- ✓ image-based rendering (IBR). This technique focuses primarily on the visual appearance of the object rather than its precise geometry. It uses photographic images to simulate 3D views, allowing for realistic visualisation from different angles without necessarily reconstructing the full 3D shape. While less accurate in terms of spatial measurements, IBR is useful for creating immersive experiences or visual effects.
- ✓ image-based modelling (IBM). Unlike IBR, image-based modelling aims to reconstruct both the shape and appearance of the object from a series of photographs. This is typically achieved through photogrammetry, where overlapping images are processed to extract 3D spatial information. IBM is widely used because it is relatively low-cost, portable, and flexible, requiring only a camera and appropriate software.
- ✓ range-based modelling. This method uses active sensors—such as laser scanners or structured light systems—that emit a signal (light or laser) and record its reflection to capture the exact distance to the object's surface. The result is a highly accurate point cloud that represents the object's geometry in three dimensions. Range-based techniques are often preferred when high precision and detail are required.
- ✓ hybrid methods combining image and range data. These approaches combine image and range data to take advantage of the strengths of both. For example, range data

Associated project to RESILIENCE

may be used to ensure geometric accuracy, while photographic images provide colour and texture for visual realism. Hybrid methods are particularly useful when both precise measurements and photorealistic visualisation are needed.

The image-based 3D modelling workflow typically follows a structured pipeline consisting of four main phases:

- ✓ Design. This initial stage involves selecting the appropriate sensors or cameras and planning the acquisition process. Decisions are based on the object's size, complexity, surface properties, and the required output (e.g., accuracy, visual quality).
- ✓ Measurement. During this phase, data are collected in the form of images, point clouds, or other geometric representations. The goal is to capture the necessary information for reconstructing the object's shape.
- ✓ Structuring. The raw data are then processed to create a structured representation. This may include segmenting the data, aligning the images or point clouds, and generating a polygonal mesh that defines the object's 3D geometry.
- ✓ Texturing and Visualisation. Finally, photographic textures are mapped onto the 3D mesh to produce a visually realistic model. This enhances both the readability and the interpretability of the model for various applications, from research to public engagement.

While the choice of modelling approach is guided by project-specific goals and available resources, the quality and accuracy of the resulting 3D models ultimately depend on how the data acquisition and processing phases are designed and executed.

Key factors include the selection of suitable sensors, the geometry of image capture, and the processing tools employed for model refinement and visualisation. A closer look at these aspects helps clarify both the potential and the limitations of digital 3D modelling in cultural heritage contexts.

Accuracy in 3D point measurement heavily depends on the design of the acquisition network, including the selection of a suitable sensor, camera type, imaging positions and orientations. Poor network design as well as the use of archival images can limit results. In such cases, calibrating the camera first under optimal conditions and applying those parameters to the object reconstruction may yield better outcomes than simultaneous calibration and modelling.

In cultural heritage, 3D mesh modelling tools are widely used to process and refine digital representations. These software applications, such as Blender, MeshLab (open source), or Agisoft Metashape, RealityCapture, ZBrush, and Rhino (commercial), allow users to create or refine 3D models based on photogrammetry or laser scan data.

Associated project to RESILIENCE

They support operations such as mesh cleaning (filling holes, removing noise), optimisation (reducing complexity), texturing (applying colour or images), segmentation, annotation, and export to formats compatible with online viewers, archives, or 3D printing.

However, mesh models represent only the external surface of an object and provide no insight into internal structures or material composition. For this reason, other diagnostic methods are often necessary. For example, X-ray radiography can reveal internal features in stone, wood, or metal objects, such as casting techniques, defects, corrosion, or restorations. Likewise, archaeometric techniques like X-ray fluorescence (XRF) can determine elemental composition, enriching the information associated with a 3D model.

It is important to note that mesh modelling can only approximate the surface of an object. This is generally sufficient when mesh resolution is high enough to capture fine details. However, higher resolution increases file size, which can create challenges for storage, rendering, and manipulation.

Digitising Cultural Heritage and the Creation of 3D Models: Methods and Challenges

The following section provides a detailed overview of the most widely used procedures for the acquisition, digitisation, and 3D modelling of cultural heritage objects. The discussion concludes with a focus on the methodology adopted for the specific case of the dataset of magical-therapeutic bowls—artefacts that present multiple challenges, not only because of their material (a copper alloy prone to surface reflectance), but also due to their shape (hemispherical vessels with thin rims), the presence of numerous inscriptions, often difficult to read or interpret, decorative motifs and symbols that are hard to decipher and not easily categorised within a digital archive.

Photogrammetry

Photogrammetry is a passive, image-based documentation technique that extracts accurate 3D geometric and textural information from photographs. It effectively transforms 2D image data into 3D data by rigorously establishing the geometric relationships between the acquired images and the physical scene as it existed at the time of capture (Remondino 2014; Bosco 2022, 7-11).

Photogrammetry works by capturing multiple images of an object from different angles—usually a minimum of two. By analysing the shifts in the object's position between these images, a phenomenon known as parallax, the software can reconstruct depth and spatial relationships.

This process makes it possible to extract three-dimensional information from the areas where the images overlap, mimicking the way human vision perceives depth through both eyes.

Associated project to RESILIENCE

Compared to other recording and modeling methods, images can be acquired with no expensive systems and contain all the information for the generation of a textured 3D model. The process begins with the acquisition of a set of high-quality photographs. These images must overlap significantly—typically by at least 60–80%—to allow the software to identify common features and calculate the spatial position. The object is photographed from multiple angles, following a systematic plan designed to ensure complete coverage of all visible surfaces. There is no strict quantitative limit to the number of photos that can be taken; however, it is important to consider that a large set of high-resolution images can significantly slow down the processing time and may put excessive strain on the hardware if it is not properly equipped.

This initial step relies on digital camera calibration, which considers several key settings such as:

- ✓ ISO, which controls the sensor's sensitivity to light,
- ✓ White balance, which adjusts colour tones based on the light temperature,
- ✓ Focus ring lock, to prevent accidental shifts in focus, ensuring consistency across shots,
- ✓ Distortion correction, to minimise optical distortions typical of certain lenses,
- ✓ Vibration reduction, which stabilises the image to counteract camera movement—particularly useful for handheld shooting or low-light conditions.

The images are then processed using photogrammetric software, which performs several steps such as:

- ✓ Image alignment or Structure-from-Motion (SfM): the software detects matching points in the photographs and calculates the relative position and orientation of each camera in space,
- ✓ Sparse point cloud generation: a preliminary 3D structure is built from the matched points,
- ✓ Dense point cloud generation: the software refines the model by estimating the depth of each pixel, resulting in a dense set of 3D points,
- ✓ Mesh creation: the point cloud is converted into a continuous surface (mesh) that represents the geometry of the object,
- ✓ Texture mapping: the original photographs are projected onto the mesh to produce a photo-realistic texture, enhancing the visual detail of the model.

As of today, image-based modelling remains the most comprehensive, cost-effective, portable, and flexible method for 3D documentation, particularly in the field of cultural heritage. Compared to 3D scanning technologies, it relies on widely available, lightweight, and affordable equipment, and can achieve accurate results across a wide range of object

sizes. One of its main advantages is its non-invasive nature: photogrammetry, the core technique behind image-based modelling, allows for detailed documentation without any physical contact. This makes it especially suitable for fragile or inaccessible objects. In addition, it can be carried out using standard digital cameras and open-source software, making it significantly more affordable than other 3D recording techniques such as laser scanning.

Lastly—and no less significantly—photogrammetry offers valuable opportunities for generating 3D models from historical documentation, namely from pre-existing photographs that were not originally acquired following standard photogrammetric protocols. This approach can prove especially useful in cases where the original artefacts have since been lost, destroyed, or are no longer accessible—whether due to armed conflict, deliberate acts of iconoclasm driven by religious or ideological fanaticism, or the natural decay of materials over time. In such scenarios, historical photographs may represent the only surviving visual record of a cultural object, and their transformation into digital 3D models offers a powerful means of preserving memory, enabling study, and even supporting potential future reconstructions (Condorelli 2022; see also the paragraph Meroitic stele as a case study).

This area of application has expanded significantly thanks to recent advances in data acquisition and processing using Structure from Motion (SfM) algorithm, which has made tools and software increasingly automated and user-friendly. These technological developments have encouraged a growing number of researchers and heritage professionals to adopt photogrammetry in their work, broadening the range of users who can rely on this method as an effective tool for analysis, study of cultural heritage.

It is however important to keep in mind, however, that although it is technically possible to generate a 3D point cloud from image sets captured in an unsystematic manner, this does not guarantee that the final output will meet the standards required for reliable metric data, nor that it will achieve the level of quality necessary for proper heritage documentation.

It should also be noted that photogrammetry is not equally well suited to all types of surfaces. Metallic objects, for instance, are often difficult to render in 3D due to their shiny, smooth, and featureless surfaces. As photogrammetric techniques continue to evolve, various strategies are being tested to improve the geometric accuracy of 3D reconstructions.

One such strategy involves coating the object with clay powder, which significantly enhances both the geometric accuracy of the reconstruction and the uniformity of the resulting mesh structures (Surmen 2025). In this context, temporary surface treatments—such as chalk powder, which must be rinsed off after scanning, or cyclododecane powder, a neutral substance that forms a water-tight layer and gradually sublimates without leaving residue—can provide viable solutions (Wood 2018). Nonetheless, institutional approval for applying such substances is not always granted, as was the case with the magical-therapeutic bowls. Photogrammetry currently stands out as an extremely versatile and effective tool for 3D modelling, combining low costs with a certain degree of automation in its procedures that

Associated project to RESILIENCE

allows its use by a wide range of cultural heritage professionals; nonetheless, some limitations remain. The quality of the results depends on external factors such as lighting and surface texture, as well as on the operator's ability to capture a sufficient and well-distributed photographic dataset. Reflective, transparent, or uniformly coloured surfaces can complicate the reconstruction process; moreover, large datasets may require significant processing time and computational resources. Although image-based modelling can produce accurate and realistic-looking models, sometimes comparable to those obtained through laser scanning, it remains a highly interactive process since most current automated methods are yet to be proven in real-world applications.

Meroitic stele as a case study

Political crises and military conflicts represent the greatest threat to cultural heritage in our times. Sites, museums, and cultural centers face drone attacks, looting, and severe damage due to lack of infrastructure and maintenance. Objects are destroyed, dispersed, or enter illegal trafficking circuits that finance military operations, with looted artefacts reaching international auction houses. This tragedy underscores the critical vulnerability of cultural heritage in conflict zones and highlights the urgent need for innovative digital technologies to preserve and reconstruct archaeological materials.

In Sudan, despite ongoing political instability since 2019 and armed conflicts in western and southern regions, the nation's cultural heritage remained largely protected until violence erupted in Khartoum in April 2023. Since then, systematic bombing, military occupation of cultural sites, and widespread looting have made heritage both a victim of war and a tool of propaganda. Artefacts from Sudanese museums have appeared in international auctions until September 2024.

Irreversible losses include significant Meroitic stelae of exceptional religious and linguistic importance. To contribute to the recovery, albeit virtually, of part of this lost heritage, we planned to reuse a series of photographs produced during epigraphic campaigns to create digital and physical replicas of some lost objects through photogrammetric technology and 3D printing. This work was conducted in collaboration with WP9⁹ for the use of equipment available at the University of Turin in order to digitally reconstruct and physically reproduce,

⁹ This work was carried out within the framework of the project ITSERR – Italian Strengthening of ESFRI RI Resilience, funded by the European Union – NextGenerationEU, under Italy's National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP), Mission 4 "Education and Research" – Component 2 "From Research to Enterprise" – Investment 3.1. CUP: B53C22001770006. However, the views and opinions expressed are solely those of the authors and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the European Commission can be held responsible for them.

through 3D printing, some stelae. The main challenge

Figure 6 Recto and Verso of the stele of Amanishakheto (I BC – IAD)

consisted in the need to reuse photographic documentation executed in 2012 and not originally intended for three-dimensional reconstruction. As a study example, we decided to reproduce a Meroitic stele of religious significance that was previously preserved at the Sudan National Museum.

This stele is important for its textual content, which could provide new clues for understanding a writing system still partially untranslated, and for its religious iconographic elements that could document ritual practices that were probably the main part of the oral practices that distinguished this ancient civilization. Although the photographs were not originally taken with the purpose of producing a three-dimensional reconstruction, their quality and completeness allow the application of advanced photogrammetric techniques to generate an accurate digital model. The work focused on image alignment and the creation of a dense point cloud generated together with the preliminary polygonal mesh.

Figure 7 Photogrammetric processing

Particular attention was given to any gaps due to limitations in the photographic documentation, as well as to the recognition of epigraphic details, essential for the scientific value of the object. Subsequently, a specific strategy was designed for the reconstruction of any missing or insufficiently aligned parts. Since due to the unavailability of photographs reproducing all parts of the object, photogrammetry was used to generate 4 distinct faces, reconstructing through modeling the entire solid structure corresponding exactly to the dimensions of the stele. This process served to create a mesh to which the individual parts could be attached for rendering. After completing the 3D digital model and verifying its accuracy and structural integrity of the stele, we proceeded to physical reproduction.

Figure 8 Recto and verso views of the 3D-printed stele

The 3D reproduction, particularly the mesh model, revealed complex epigraphic signs difficult to distinguish through direct visual examination or photographic documentation,

Associated project to RESILIENCE

while the subsequent 3D printing greatly enhanced the perception and definition of these almost invisible graphic features.

The activity, although conducted at an experimental level and on a photographic archive acquired with traditional documentation objectives and not for 3D rendering, demonstrated how technology provides the possibility to ensure that significant historical artefacts remain accessible to future generations of both the general public and researchers.

Laser scanner

3D laser scanning is a non-contact active technology aimed at capturing data of the shape of real-world objects for the creation of three-dimensional models of them.

In recent years, 3D laser scanning has emerged as one of the most promising and effective technologies for the documentation and preservation of cultural heritage. Primarily used to document landscapes and buildings—which can be massive in scale, inaccessible, or in a state of disrepair—it has more recently also been applied to the documentation of historically and artistically valuable objects, as well as texts produced on various media. For example, within the ITSERR project, it has been employed by WP9 for the recording of cuneiform clay tablets (Diara 2024; Diara et al. 2024). Along with photogrammetry, this scanning methodology has proven to be a successful solution for 3D documenting archaeological finds because of its reliability. The grid pattern light typical of these sensors is, in fact, able to hit and register complex surfaces: the trigonometric triangulation occurred between the light source, the camera and the surveyed object allow to record the incidence angle (α) as well as distances. This technique offers a non-invasive means of recording the physical characteristics of the object, regardless of its size and with remarkably high accuracy.

The methodology behind 3D laser scanning relies on emitting laser beams to record vast numbers of data points by precisely measuring the distance between the scanner and the object's surface. This is achieved by calculating the time it takes for each laser pulse to travel to the surface and return, thereby determining depth. These measurements are collected from multiple vantage points and merged to form a dense and highly detailed 3D point cloud. This digital dataset provides a faithful geometric representation of the heritage asset, preserving even the finest surface details. Once processed, the point cloud can be transformed into comprehensive 3D models that accurately reflect the size, shape, texture, and spatial configuration of the structure. These models are invaluable tools for heritage professionals, as they enable precise analysis, visualisation, and monitoring of architectural elements from all angles. Researchers can explore structural conditions without direct contact, identify signs of degradation or deformation, and track subtle changes over time—capabilities that are particularly relevant in the context of conservation planning and preventive maintenance. Moreover, the availability of such high-resolution digital replicas

Associated project to RESILIENCE

opens up new avenues for restoration, structural analysis, and virtual reconstruction. Architects and engineers can simulate intervention strategies before applying them on-site, while educators and cultural institutions can use the 3D models to create immersive learning experiences and virtual tours. In short, laser scanning not only supports the practical needs of heritage conservation, but also contributes to broader goals of accessibility, public engagement, and long-term digital preservation. As the technology continues to evolve—becoming faster, more portable, and increasingly affordable—it is expected to play an even more central role in the documentation strategies adopted by heritage institutions around the world.

The application of 3D laser scanning in the documentation of cultural heritage relies on a range of technologies, each characterised by specific operational principles and suited to particular contexts and scales of intervention.

Among these, three fundamental types of laser scanners are commonly employed:

- ✓ triangulation-based scanners,
- ✓ time-of-flight (TOF) scanners,
- ✓ phase difference-based scanners.

Each offers distinct advantages in terms of precision, range, and suitability for different types of heritage assets.

Triangulation-based laser scanners operate by projecting a laser beam or structured light pattern onto the surface of an object and detecting the deformation of the pattern through one or more cameras. The deviation of the laser spot or pattern from its expected position is used to calculate precise 3D coordinates through triangulation. These scanners are particularly effective for close-range acquisition and are capable of capturing minute surface details with high spatial resolution. As such, they are ideally suited to the documentation of small- to medium-scale heritage objects, including intricate architectural ornamentation, sculptural elements, and epigraphic features. For small objects, like many of the exhibits preserved in museums, active triangulation sensors (laser or structured light) are likely the most feasible and reliable digitization solutions.

Time-of-Flight (TOF) Laser Scanners, also known as pulse-based scanners, emit rapid pulses of laser light and measure the time taken for each pulse to travel to the surface and return to the sensor. This time delay is used to calculate distance and, by extension, the three-dimensional geometry of the scanned environment. Due to their long-range capabilities and efficient data acquisition rates, TOF scanners are particularly well-suited for the documentation of extensive architectural complexes, landscapes, and large monuments. They are frequently employed in survey campaigns involving façades, open-air archaeological sites, and the volumetric analysis of built heritage.

Phase difference-based scanners determine distances by measuring the phase shift between emitted and reflected continuous-wave laser beams. This technique allows for high precision

Associated project to RESILIENCE

and rapid data acquisition, particularly over medium ranges.

The high accuracy and resolution achieved make these scanners especially appropriate for the recording of fragile or geometrically complex heritage features, such as fine sculptural decorations, deteriorated surfaces, or elaborately carved interiors. Their application is common in conservation-oriented projects where detailed dimensional analysis is required. In addition to these three main categories, the growing development of portable or handheld laser scanners has significantly expanded the range of practical applications for 3D laser scanning, particularly in the documentation of small or fragile heritage objects. One of the key advantages of handheld systems lies in their portability and ease of use, especially in confined spaces such as museum galleries or storage facilities, where traditional scanning setups may be impractical. These scanners do not require fixed lighting conditions or large operational areas, making them especially suitable for in situ documentation.

Handheld laser scanners—whether based on structured light or laser triangulation—are capable of producing high-resolution 3D models that include both geometric and chromatic data. This dual capacity makes them effective tools not only for conservation documentation but also for exhibition, education, and digital outreach. Their flexibility also allows for the rapid acquisition of complex surfaces from multiple angles, often without the need to move the object itself—an important benefit when dealing with fragile or valuable artefacts.

However, this technique does have limitations. Reflective, glossy, or translucent surfaces—such as polished metals, glass, or glazed ceramics—can pose serious challenges for handheld scanning, leading to incomplete or distorted models. In such cases, pre-treatment with matting sprays or the use of complementary digitisation techniques (e.g., photogrammetry) may be required to achieve acceptable results. Despite these constraints, portable laser scanners remain a versatile and increasingly accessible solution in the field of cultural heritage, bridging the gap between high-end laboratory analysis and practical, on-site documentation needs.

One of the main advantages of handheld laser scanning is the portability of the equipment, which allows for easy use in museums or storage facilities — especially since these scanners require neither special lighting conditions nor large working spaces, an important consideration in such environments. In addition to this flexibility, handheld scanners can produce reliable models that accurately capture both surface geometry and colour data. However, when dealing with glossy, transparent, or reflective surfaces, the method presents notable challenges.

Reflectance Transformation Imaging (RTI) and Virtual RTI

While 3D scanning and photogrammetry provide valuable information about the overall geometry and spatial features of artefacts, other imaging techniques are better suited to capturing subtle surface details that are often invisible to the naked eye. Among these,

Associated project to RESILIENCE

Reflectance Transformation Imaging (RTI) stands out for its ability to document and enhance fine textures, inscriptions, and tool marks with remarkable clarity (Bosco, Minucci 2019).

Reflectance Transformation Imaging (RTI) is a computational photographic technique that is increasingly adopted in the study and preservation of cultural heritage¹⁰. RTI is particularly effective for the documentation and analysis of inscribed and engraved objects, including stone artefacts, numismatics, cylinder seals and tablets,¹¹ and for imaging the texture of parchment or papyrus. Its versatility makes it a highly valued tool in the field of cultural heritage, with a wide range of applications spanning from the study to the conservation of ancient artefacts of various kinds.

As with photogrammetry, RTI involves capturing photographs that are taken from one stationary position, while the surface of the subject is illuminated from different raking light positions in each shot. Specially developed software compiles surface reflectance and texture information from the entire image set on a pixel-by-pixel basis. These images are processed using open-source software created by the non-profit organization Cultural Heritage Imaging (CHI 2011, 2013a–b, 2014), originally developed by Hewlett-Packard (Caine, Maggen, Altaratz 2019). The resulting output, referred to as an RTI file, can be opened using dedicated viewing software that enables the subject to be interactively re-lit producing an interactive, relightable image that reveals surface details—such as tool marks, inscriptions, and wear patterns—that are often difficult to detect under standard lighting conditions.

Specialised processing software utilises surface normal information to calculate the deflection of light rays on a virtual 3D surface. Although this is technically a 2D recording approach, it is often described as 2½D because of the high-level visual information provided by highlighting and shadowing of 3D surfaces. In particular, it approximates the surface orientation at each pixel, providing a relative measure of curvature. Using colour data stored per pixel, as well as the captured surface normal information, this technique reveals surface texture and fine detail sometimes not captured by static photography or even obvious to the naked eye.

Its ease of use and reliance on common low-cost equipment make this method sufficiently versatile and accessible at different levels. The preferred acquisition method in archaeology is Highlight-Based RTI (H-RTI). This approach requires a standard camera, a tripod, and an external light source, such as a wireless flash or continuous light. A reflective target is essential for successful acquisition. This target consists of a glossy, dark-coloured sphere or hemisphere (one or two can be used), positioned near the object being recorded. The sphere

¹⁰ User-friendly guidelines and advice on recording cultural heritage could be found in Historic England 2018 *Multi-light Imaging for Cultural Heritage*. Swindon: Historic England, <https://historicengland.org.uk/images-books/publications/multi-light-imaging-heritage-applications/heag069-multi-light-imaging/>

¹¹ About this, see Cuneiform Digital Library Initiative (CDLI, still active: <https://cdli.ucla.edu> and in particular, <https://cdli.earth/postings/161>).

Associated project to RESILIENCE

must remain fixed in its position and visible in every frame. The target's function is to capture the light source position through direct reflection on its surface. The light source should move around the area of interest at angles between 15° and 65°, forming a sort of dome. Each light position corresponds to a separate camera shot, with the camera maintaining a fixed viewpoint on the object. For optimal acquisition and high-quality photographic datasets, it is crucial to avoid vibrations or movement during the capture process. Additionally, the light source should be positioned at a distance at least twice the diameter of the object being recorded. Due to the transportable kit and robust software, the technique is flexible enough to be used in many recording scenarios, such as at remote sites and on horizontal and vertical surfaces. RTI can be successfully used on surfaces from around 2m diameter down to a microscopic level. The method can also be virtually replicated and can even be used underwater, and it is often applied outdoors for the acquisition of inscriptions and rock reliefs in order to improve the reading, and thus the interpretation, of the signs and to better understand the processes of their creation. Another acquisition method involves the use of a light dome (D-RTI). This consists of a physical dome, made of metal or plastic, with an upper opening for the camera and internally mounted LEDs placed at predefined distances to illuminate the object from multiple equidistant points. The LEDs are synchronized with the camera shots, maximizing automation and minimizing direct handling of the camera. This method is particularly suited for small objects, and it is generally used in laboratory settings. The dome's inherent stability and semi-automated capture process eliminate the risk of motion, ensuring sharp, high-quality images free from blur-related artefacts, which could otherwise compromise the final data processing.

Conveniently, on a personal computer, it allows users to relight an object from different directions, emphasizing surface features, even microscopic ones, that would otherwise be difficult to observe under natural lighting conditions.

The limitations of this technique stem primarily from the fact that, while it offers highly detailed qualitative information about surface texture, it does not generate metric 3D data. Such data can instead be acquired through other methods, including photogrammetric survey or laser scanning (see above).

Although this approach excels at capturing fine surface detail, it cannot reveal visual features—such as colour or texture—that are obscured by overlying materials like lichen or paint. In other words, unless there is a measurable difference in surface relief, the technique cannot detect what lies beneath. In such cases, multi-spectral imaging methods, including ultraviolet (UV) or infrared (IR) photography, may offer better results.

Recent developments in RTI research suggest that multi-spectral datasets can be integrated using specialised RTI software, expanding the range of detectable features. To achieve optimal surface detail, it is recommended that the subject not exceed approximately 2 metres in diameter. However, with appropriate equipment, even microscopic objects can be documented.

Associated project to RESILIENCE

When segmenting a larger surface is not feasible, alternative techniques like photogrammetry or laser scanning may be more suitable. Although some practitioners have experimented with stitching together multiple RTI datasets, the final quality of the rendering ultimately depends on the quality of the source images. The processing software is relatively versatile and allows for some adjustments in post-production, but it cannot compensate for data not captured during the initial recording phase.

The Virtual RTI (V-RTI) methodology was developed to overcome the acquisition challenges encountered in traditional RTI, leveraging the increasingly widespread and well-structured 3D surveying workflow used in archaeology.

The technique involves the creation of a virtual dome within the open-source software Blender, simulating the technical characteristics of a real dome while allowing for adaptable dimensions depending on the object being acquired. The object itself is placed in the virtual environment as a 3D replica, obtained through photogrammetric surveying or laser scanning, and imported in OBJ format.

Next to the object, a virtual reflective sphere is positioned, created by generating a primitive UV Sphere with a high number of geometry subdivisions to ensure maximum smoothness, complemented by smooth-shaded normals. Additionally, the sphere's shadow can be disabled, preventing it from being projected onto the object's surface. The entire setup accurately replicates a real-world RTI acquisition, with the camera positioned at the top of the dome, near the uppermost ring of lights. Each light position corresponds to a captured image, and the final dataset can be processed as usual using RTI software such as RelightLab available online at <https://vcg.isti.cnr.it/relight/#download>.

This virtual methodology combines the geometric detail of high-resolution 3D models with the micro-relief analysis capabilities of RTI, providing a powerful tool for archaeological research.

However, it is essential to note that the quality of the results depends strictly on the resolution of the 3D replica being used. The 3D mesh must have a high level of geometric detail to ensure that the light projection and subsequent application of filters linked to specific fitting algorithms - such as PTM (Polynomial Texture Mapping) or HSH (Hemispherical Harmonics) - yield relevant and accurate results.

Within the ITSERR project, WP10 tested RTI on this relocated panel, carved with complex figurative and symbolic scenes. The technique proved especially effective in enhancing the legibility and interpretability of the engravings (Bosco *et al.*, in print).

RTI has shown particular value in rock art research, a field that has long relied on traditional documentation methods such as scale drawings, tracings from photographs, or direct tracings made on poly-vinyl sheets using permanent markers—often aided by oblique light. In more recent years, digital photographs combined with vector graphic software (e.g., Adobe Illustrator, Corel Draw) have supported these practices. However, these techniques are limited in both precision and analytical potential. They tend to flatten surfaces into static, two-dimensional renderings, offering little help in capturing the physical subtleties of

Associated project to RESILIENCE

engravings—many of which are shallow, eroded, or stylistically complex. Environmental conditions such as lighting and weather can further compromise data quality. Most critically, these methods struggle to represent the inherently three-dimensional nature of rock art surfaces.

In contrast, RTI allows for the dynamic visualisation of surface textures by enabling users to re-light the object interactively in a virtual space. This capability reveals fine details—such as carving techniques, tool marks, and depth variations—that would otherwise be missed in standard documentation. RTI thus provides essential support for both interpretative analysis and condition assessment.

Moreover, the integration of RTI into digital outreach strategies further strengthens its value. Interactive touchscreens installed in museums or visitor centres can display high-resolution RTI renderings and photogrammetric 3D models, making rock art accessible to all audiences—without the need for specialised equipment or on-site access. These interfaces allow users to explore the engraved surface by rotating, zooming, and relighting it, while layered annotations, photographic close-ups, and multimedia content can offer contextual insights into motifs, techniques, and cultural meanings. Such installations reduce the need for physical interaction with fragile surfaces, supporting conservation, while also providing inclusive access to remote or immobile audiences.

Beyond documentation and accessibility, RTI contributes meaningfully to interpretation. By revealing visual information that escapes direct observation, it opens new perspectives on the symbolic, aesthetic, and narrative dimensions of the engravings. In this way, digital tools do not merely compensate for the loss of original context—they actively enrich our understanding and appreciation of the artwork, transforming it into a dynamic, evolving resource for both research and public engagement.

The magic-therapeutic bowls as a case study

One of the aims of the ReTina research group was the digital acquisition of a selection of Islamic magic-therapeutic bowls from the remarkable private Aron Collection, recently donated to the Museo Universitario Orientale “Umberto Scerrato”.

Fourteen of these bowls have already been studied and published in the monograph *The Aron Collection. Islamic Magic-Therapeutic Bowls* by Roberta Giunta (2018). They were also featured in the exhibition *Le coppe magiche islamiche del Museo Orientale Umberto Scerrato*, curated by Michele Bernardini, Roberta Giunta, Carlotta Passaro, and Veronica Prestini, and later published in the catalogue *The Aron Donation: A Collection of Islamic Magic Bowls* (2025) by Michele Bernardini and Roberta Giunta.

These artefacts represent a particularly rich case study due to the complex interaction of text, symbolism, form, and material. Digitisation is not only a means of documentation, but a methodological opportunity to explore surface inscriptions, object function, and conservation needs through integrated 3D approaches.

Two different workflows were tested. The first followed a traditional photogrammetric approach using a digital camera; the second involved a selection of objects scanned with a Creality Otter 3D laser scanner and processed using Creality Scan software.

This second method was trialed in order to assess the performance of laser scanning on complex objects—such as those with concave/convex shapes and reflective metallic surfaces—which are known to pose challenges in photogrammetric processing. However, the results proved unsatisfactory: the scanner struggled to acquire complete geometry, especially in merging the inner and outer surfaces. Furthermore, the textures generated were inconsistent and blurred due to the reflective nature of the metal.

Given these limitations, photogrammetry was adopted as the primary strategy. The bowls were digitized using a Nikon D750 FX DSLR camera (24.3 MP full-frame sensor, 24–120mm f/4 lens), mounted on a tripod to allow for controlled exposure times.

Image acquisition took place in the storage rooms of the Umberto Scerrato University Museum of Oriental Studies, where the bowls are temporarily housed while awaiting the museum’s new exhibition setup scheduled for late 2025.

Each bowl was placed inside a lightbox on a rotating turntable covered with white sheets to ensure a neutral background. The object was rotated by at least 1/16 of a full turn between shots.

The lightbox setup proved highly effective: the cold, diffuse, and evenly distributed light eliminated harsh shadows and strong reflections, improving image readability and facilitating accurate feature matching by the photogrammetry software.

Two separate photo sets were captured for each bowl—one for the inner surface and one for the outer. To ensure sufficient overlap between the two sets, the bowls were placed on inclined supports that allowed both surfaces to be visible from various angles.

Despite the complexity of the object shapes, no physical markers were placed on the surfaces. Instead, identifiable control points—such as decorative details, inscriptions, symbols, or surface defects visible in both sets—were used during processing to assist in aligning and merging the models.

Table 4 Characteristics of the Acquired Photographs

Resolution	6016 x 4016
DPI	300dpi
F-stop	F/11
Exposure time	1/4sec.
ISO	ISO-100
Focal distance	50cm

Photogrammetric Processing

Associated project to RESILIENCE

The photographs were processed using two photogrammetric software packages: Agisoft Metashape and the open-source RealityCapture. Metashape was unable to align a sufficient number of images for most of the objects. RealityCapture, by contrast, proved more effective for both alignment and 3D reconstruction.

Given the shape and reflective properties of the bowls, the inner and outer surfaces were processed independently. In some cases—particularly with smaller bowls, flatter objects, or when bulkier supports were used—it was necessary to mask the images, isolating the object and removing background areas to improve alignment.

The resulting point clouds from the two separate sets were then imported into a single project.

Figure 9 M01152, Point cloud generated after image alignment

During this stage, shared control points were identified—specific inscriptions, motifs, or surface anomalies that appeared in both clouds—and used to merge the two components into a unified model. A complete mesh was then generated, to which texture mapping was applied.

Associated project to RESILIENCE

Figure 10 MO1152, placement of control points on the point cloud

Workflow Summary

- ✓ Image acquisition using a DSLR camera
- ✓ Camera calibration and image orientation, using automatic procedures to detect homologous points and estimate camera parameters
- ✓ Dense matching and 3D reconstruction to generate detailed point clouds
- ✓ Polygonal model generation and texture mapping for analysis and visualization

Outcomes and Future Applications

The digital replicas produced are not only valuable for research and documentation but also open up new opportunities for conservation, education, and public engagement. By providing highly accurate 3D models, digitalisation enables remote access to complex artefacts, facilitates condition monitoring over time, and supports interdisciplinary studies that integrate textual, material, and morphological data.

Thanks to the collaboration with WP9, one model was successfully transformed into tangible replicas through high-resolution 3D printing. The physical reproductions serve multiple functions: they allow for close-up, tactile exploration in educational settings; they can be safely handled by students, scholars, and visitors without risking damage to the originals; and they offer valuable tools for exhibition design and audience interaction, especially in inclusive or multisensory display contexts.

Moreover, the ability to produce accurate physical surrogates supports risk management and conservation planning. Replicas can be used in place of originals in outreach events or temporary displays, ensuring the protection of fragile artefacts while still making their form and significance accessible to diverse audiences.

Associated project to RESILIENCE

A significant example of this approach was the multisensory tour held on 9 April 2025, as part of the exhibition *Le coppe magiche islamiche del Museo Orientale Umberto Scerrato*. The event was specifically designed for blind and visually impaired visitors, who were guided by R. Giunta, L. De Maio, and C. Passaro through a cultural experience structured around a multisensory approach. The tour incorporated tactile, olfactory, auditory, allowing participants to engage with the objects and their meanings in an inclusive and immersive way.

In this context, the use of 3D-printed replicas of the bowls would be essential: it could allow direct physical interaction with the shapes and inscriptions of the artefacts, which would otherwise be inaccessible. These replicas thus could play a key role in enhancing the accessibility and educational value of the museum's collection through innovative and inclusive interpretation strategies.

From Model to Matter: The Role of Archaeometry in Artefact Interpretation

Archaeometry represents one of the most dynamic and innovative fields within contemporary archaeological research. Arising from the intersection of the humanities and the so-called hard sciences—a commonly used but somewhat imprecise label—it brings together methods and analytical tools from chemistry, physics, geology, and computer science to explore ancient materials and archaeological contexts (Castellano, Martini, Sibilina 2007).

While initially focused on prehistoric contexts, archaeometry has become increasingly central to the study of historical periods as well. Through physico-chemical analyses—most often carried out using non-destructive techniques—it offers powerful means to investigate the composition, origin, and dating of artefacts, as well as the technological choices, production processes, and exchange systems behind their creation and circulation.

Characterization of Artefacts

The study of artefact composition is one of the most common applications of archaeometry. Through physico-chemical analysis, it is possible to determine which materials make up an object—for example, the types of clay used for a ceramic vessel, the alloys in a metal tool, or the pigments in a decoration. This type of knowledge goes far beyond simple cataloguing and classification, as it allows researchers to reconstruct production techniques, identify the sources of raw materials, and understand the technological and cultural choices made by those who created the artefact.

Analyzing the composition of an object can provide valuable information about trade networks, cultural interactions, and regional practices, as well as insights into the functional use of materials and their symbolic associations, for instance their connection to elite status or culturally specific meanings attributed to certain substances.

Contribution for Conservation

Knowledge gained through archaeometric analysis is also crucial for conservation efforts. Understanding the material composition and structural characteristics of an object is the foundation for developing appropriate preservation strategies. This knowledge helps identify vulnerabilities—such as sensitivity to environmental conditions, chemical instability, or previous restoration interventions—and informs the choice of compatible conservation materials and techniques. In this way, archaeometry supports not only the long-term protection of artefacts but also the planning of preventive measures tailored to their specific needs.

Chronological Frameworks and Dating Methods

Archaeometry also plays a key role in dating archaeological finds, offering scientific methods capable of determining when an object was produced or an event took place. This support is particularly valuable in cases where written sources or direct chronological references are lacking, or when the context of discovery is unknown.

Moreover, analyses can contribute significantly to the dating of archaeological finds and contexts through a range of scientific methods that complement and enhance traditional archaeological observations. These techniques provide independent chronological data that can confirm, refine, or challenge hypotheses based on typology or stratigraphy. Among the most widely used approaches are radiometric dating methods, which rely on the measurable decay of radioactive isotopes to estimate the age of organic or inorganic materials.

The most familiar of these is radiocarbon dating (^{14}C), which is particularly effective for dating organic remains such as charcoal, bone, wood, or seeds up to about 50,000 years old. For materials that cannot be dated using radiocarbon—such as ceramics, burnt flints, or sediments—alternative techniques like thermoluminescence (TL) and optically stimulated luminescence (OSL) are employed. These methods determine the last time a material was heated or exposed to sunlight, respectively, making them particularly useful in archaeological contexts where fire or burial processes have played a significant role.

The integration of these dating methods with archaeological interpretation not only improves the accuracy of chronological frameworks but also allows for a better understanding of site formation processes, the duration of human activities, and the temporal relationships between different occupation phases. In cases where stratigraphy is disturbed, written sources are absent, or the provenance of finds is uncertain, archaeometric dating becomes an indispensable tool for reconstructing the past with greater precision.

Analytical Techniques and Applications

In addition to chronological assessment, archaeometry encompasses a wide range of analytical techniques aimed at investigating the composition and transformation of

Associated project to RESILIENCE

materials over time. These methods provide crucial information not only for dating but also for understanding the technologies, uses, and meanings associated with archaeological objects.

Techniques such as X-ray fluorescence (XRF), Raman spectroscopy, and Fourier-Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FT-IR) allow researchers to study the composition and structure of materials at both macro and micro scales, often without the need for sampling or any damage to the artefacts. These non-destructive or minimally invasive methods are particularly valuable for the analysis of ceramics, metals, pigments, glasses, and lithic artefacts.

Microscopic observation—using both optical microscopy and scanning electron microscopy (SEM), often coupled with energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS)—further contributes to the study of manufacturing techniques, surface treatments, and degradation processes. In addition, the use of portable instruments enables in situ analysis, expanding the possibilities for material characterisation while preserving the integrity of the objects.

Beyond the study of individual artefacts, archaeometric methods also support the reconstruction of past environments, including aspects such as climate conditions, resource exploitation, and site formation processes. These approaches, in turn, provide valuable insights into human behaviours such as craft specialisation, mobility, and cultural interaction, integrating scientific data with archaeological interpretation within an interdisciplinary framework.

While most commonly applied to inorganic materials, archaeometry also shows growing potential in the analysis of organic substances—particularly in ritual and religious contexts. Although such materials fall outside the scope of techniques like XRF or FT-IR, they can be investigated through complementary methods, such as organic residue analysis and molecular characterisation. These approaches can help identify the contents or traces of materials once held within artefacts, shedding light on symbolic, therapeutic, or ceremonial uses.

Among its many potential applications, archaeometry could significantly contribute to the study of ritual practices—an area of particular interest within WP10 of the ITSERR project. Although no specific analyses have yet been carried out on ritual materials in this context, future investigations could explore the composition of substances used as offerings—such as resins, oils, or animal fats—providing insights into sacrificial practices and the cultural or symbolic criteria behind material selection.

Similarly, organic residue analysis might be applied to ceremonial vessels—such as libation bowls or magic-therapeutic bowls—with the aim of detecting traces of substances believed to possess magical or healing properties, including aromatic plants, psychoactive ingredients, or medicinal compounds. While these types of analyses are methodologically complex and have not yet been implemented in this case study, they represent promising avenues for investigating the material and performative dimensions of ritual behaviour.

Amulets also represent an important category examined within WP10, often composed of a wide variety of materials and charged with protective or apotropaic meanings.

Archaeometric analysis of these objects contributes to the understanding of material choices, production techniques, and symbolic associations, complementing the study of ritual vessels. Together, these findings deepen our comprehension of how matter and meaning were interwoven in ritual performance—and how specific materials were intentionally selected not only for their sensory or practical qualities, but also for their perceived spiritual efficacy.

Finally, archaeometry plays a critical role not only in investigating the past but also in the preservation and conservation of cultural heritage. Increasingly, scientific techniques are employed in conservation efforts through non-destructive methods such as infrared thermography, computed tomography (CT scanning), and reflectography, which allow conservators to detect structural anomalies—such as cracks, internal voids, or corrosion—without physically intervening on the objects.

In addition to chronological assessment, archaeometry encompasses a wide range of analytical techniques aimed at investigating the composition and transformation of materials over time. These methods provide crucial information not only for dating but also for understanding the technologies, uses, and meanings associated with archaeological objects. Techniques such as X-ray fluorescence (XRF), Raman spectroscopy, and Fourier-Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FT-IR) allow researchers to investigate the composition and structure of materials at both macro and micro scales, often without requiring sampling or causing any damage to the artefacts. These non-destructive or minimally invasive methods are particularly valuable for the analysis of ceramics, metals, pigments, glasses, and lithic artefacts.

Microscopic observation—using both optical microscopy and scanning electron microscopy (SEM), often coupled with energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS)—further contributes to the study of manufacturing techniques, surface treatments, and degradation processes. In addition, the use of portable instruments enables in situ analysis, expanding the possibilities for characterizing materials while preserving their integrity.

Beyond individual artefacts, archaeometric approaches contribute to the reconstruction of past environments, including aspects such as climate conditions, resource exploitation, and site formation processes. In this way, they also shed light on human behaviours, such as craft specialization, mobility, and cultural interactions, integrating scientific data with archaeological interpretation in a profoundly interdisciplinary framework.

Analytical Instruments within ITSERR Project

Although such analyses remain prospective, their feasibility has been greatly enhanced thanks to the acquisition of specialised equipment by WP10 of the ITSERR project. These resources allow for the investigation of both organic and inorganic materials through non-

destructive or minimally invasive techniques, laying the groundwork for future in-depth studies of ritual artefacts and their contents.

To support this research potential and improve the quality of analytical data, WP10 acquired a suite of high-performance instruments, including a digital microscope with advanced lighting and imaging modes capable of revealing even the most subtle surface features, and three portable spectrometers for the chemical and structural analysis of ancient materials.

Specifically, the acquisitions included a digital microscope offering a wide range of imaging and analysis functions (Keyence, VHX-X1 Series), an X-ray fluorescence (XRF) spectrometer (Bruker Tracer 5), a Raman spectrometer (Bruker Bravo), and an FT-IR spectrometer (Alpha II), each designed for a specific type of analysis.

The XRF (X-ray fluorescence) spectrometer is a tool commonly used in archaeometry to analyse the elemental composition of a material in a non-destructive way. It serves to identify the chemical elements present on the surface of an object and to determine the composition of metal alloys, as well as of ceramics, glass, enamels, pigments, or soils. The resulting data can be used to compare objects in order to investigate their provenance or manufacturing techniques, and to determine, for example, whether certain metal objects, such as for example the magic-therapeutic bowls that make up one of our datasets, with apparently similar features were produced in the same workshop or not.

Likewise, XRF spectrometry can provide information about ceramic composition, for example to assess whether artefacts were produced locally using local clays or imported. In the field of cultural heritage, XRF analysis can also be applied to identify modern interventions, contaminations, or past restorations, and to monitor the condition of metal objects by analysing surface alterations or corrosion products.

XRF technology could also be used to investigate the original contents of ancient containers, such as ceramic or metal vessels. The instrument can detect traces of elements probably associated with substances once stored in the containers, such as phosphorus, sulphur, or chlorine, indicative of foodstuffs, beverages, or other organic materials, as well as inorganic residues such as salts or minerals. In the case of vessels with magic-therapeutic functions, the presence of heavy metals such as lead or mercury may point to specific uses, including medicinal or cosmetic preparations.

The Raman spectrometer is a widely used tool in archaeometry for identifying molecules and chemical compounds through the analysis of their molecular vibrations, in a non-destructive way and without the need for sampling. This instrument operates by detecting the light scattered (Raman scattering) when a sample is illuminated by a laser light source. The scattered light contains information about the molecular vibrations of the sample, effectively providing a unique spectral fingerprint for each substance. In this way, it becomes possible to identify chemical compounds and obtain detailed information about molecular structures, including the types of chemical bonds present and their interactions.

The Raman spectrometer is used to identify mineral and ceramic pigments on pottery, frescoes, textiles, and papyri; to distinguish between very similar dyes; and to study both

Associated project to RESILIENCE

organic and inorganic materials such as resins, waxes, amber, and minerals. In the case of glass, the instrument allows researchers to analyze its structural components as well as the colouring or decorative treatments applied to the object. The technique also makes it possible to detect alterations and degradation products and to distinguish between natural materials and synthetic substances introduced during restoration.

Finally, the FT-IR spectrometer—short for Fourier-Transform Infrared—is another widely used instrument in archaeometry for identifying organic and inorganic compounds based on their response to infrared radiation. By analyzing how molecules absorb IR light, it produces a characteristic absorption spectrum for each material. This makes it possible to identify organic substances such as waxes or bituminous materials, as well as glues, lacquers, and oils, along with food residues or organic contents on ceramics, including fats, proteins, and carbohydrates.

Porous materials, such as ceramics, have the capacity to absorb liquid and semi-liquid substances with which they come into contact and to retain them over time. The identification of these absorbed contents can provide valuable insights into the use and function of vessels, while also offering important information on dietary practices, culinary habits, and trade networks. For example, the ability to detect specific substances in prehistoric containers allows researchers to date the introduction of certain foodstuffs into the human diet—such as the earliest use of wine or dairy products. Similarly, the differential enrichment of various parts of a cooking vessel can shed light on food preparation techniques, indicating whether food was boiled, roasted, or prepared in other ways. Residue analysis can also contribute to our understanding of social organization and status, as it is often the differential access to particular foodstuffs—rather than the ceramic types themselves—that reflects social distinctions.

[Beyond the Model: Archaeometric Investigations of Magic-Therapeutic Bowls. A Potential Case Study](#)

While formal and typological models remain essential for archaeological interpretation, they often represent only the “outer shell” of our understanding. Archaeometry allows us to delve deeper into the material realities of objects, their manufacturing techniques, and the cultural logics embedded in their production. This approach is particularly relevant for the magic-therapeutic bowls, inscribed metal vessels linked to healing or protective functions and central to the ITSERR project.

Given their metallic nature, these bowls offer a privileged field for archaeometric analysis. Metals, rarely used in their pure form, require sophisticated technological knowledge throughout extraction, alloying, casting, finishing, and surface treatment phases. Elemental and isotopic analyses—primarily via portable XRF spectrometers (like the Bruker Tracer 5)

Associated project to RESILIENCE

and, where possible, lead isotope fingerprinting—enable precise characterization of the metal alloys and raw material sources.

Such analyses could provide several key insights:

- ✓ Alloy Composition and Technological Choices: Determining the precise alloy composition (bronze, brass, leaded bronze, arsenical copper, etc.) helps distinguish intentional metallurgical recipes from accidental impurities, shedding light on technological traditions and choices
- ✓ Raw Material Provenance: Isotopic and multivariate analyses can trace the origin of metal sources, allowing identification of ore deposits and supply networks. This can reveal whether the bowls were produced locally or imported, allowing to reconstruct trade routes and supply networks
- ✓ Identification of Workshops and Artisan Schools: By comparing elemental compositions, isotope data, and metallographic features—such as microstructures observable through scanning electron microscopy (SEM) coupled with energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS)—it is possible to group bowls according to shared production traits. These clusters may correspond to specific workshops, craft traditions, or regional schools, helping to reconstruct ancient production landscapes and artisan network. Although a SEM is not currently among the instruments provided within the ITSERR project, the initiative does contribute to the renovation of laboratory spaces that are intended to host such equipment in the future. It is worth noting, however, that SEM analysis presents certain physical constraints: most models, including the one the project aims to acquire, cannot accommodate samples exceedingly approximately 15 cm in size. As a result, this technique may not be applicable to the analysis of larger artefacts such as the magic-therapeutic bowls, unless sampling is considered—an approach generally not feasible for objects of this kind due to their integrity and heritage value.
- ✓ Material and Ritual Significance: The deliberate use of certain elements (e.g., lead or mercury) may reflect specific ritual or therapeutic purposes. Combining archaeometric data with organic residue analysis can deepen understanding of the bowls' symbolic and functional roles

Within the ITSERR project, the availability of advanced analytical instruments—including portable XRF and Raman spectrometers, as well as FT-IR—facilitates a comprehensive, minimally invasive study of these vessels.

A proposed workflow involves:

- ✓ Initial non-destructive elemental analysis by portable XRF to classify alloy types and detect surface alterations or restorations.

Finanziato
dall'Unione europea
NextGenerationEU

Associated project to RESILIENCE

- ✓ Follow-up Raman and FT-IR analyses to identify pigments, corrosion products, or organic residues.
- ✓ Selective microscopic examination (SEM-EDS) of small samples, when feasible, to investigate metallurgical microstructures and manufacturing techniques.
- ✓ Integration of archaeometric data with epigraphic and stylistic information to identify production groups and reconstruct workshop practices.

By combining these approaches, archaeometry moves beyond typological models to provide a nuanced picture of the production, circulation, and ritual use of magic-therapeutic bowls—opening windows onto ancient technological expertise, cultural identities, and the interplay between matter and meaning.

References

Bernardini M., R. Giunta (2025) *The Aron Donation: A Collection of Islamic Magic Bowls*. Napoli: Quaderni delle Collezioni Museali de "L'Orientale".

Bosco A. (2022) *3D Surveying Methods and Digital Information Management for Archaeological Heritage*. BAR International Series 3091. Oxford: Archaeopress.

Bosco A., E. Minucci (2019) La metodologia RTI in contesto archeologico: il caso di un graffito nelle Catacombe di San Gennaro (Napoli). *Newsletter di Archeologia CISA* 10, 115-136.

Bosco A., D. De Luca, A. Pavan, R. Valentini (in print) From Stone to Screen: Applying Virtual Reflectance Transformation Imaging (V-RTI) Methodology to Rock Art in Dhofar, Southern Oman. *Groma: Documenting Archaeology*.

Caine M., M. Maggen, D. Altaratz (2019) Combining RTI & SFM. A Multi-Faceted Approach to Inscription Analysis. Conference paper presented at Electronic Imaging and the Visual Arts. Florence 2019.
[Researchgate.net/publication/333017139_Combining_RTI_SFM_A_Multi-Faceted_approach_to_Inscription_Analysis_COMBINING_RTI_SFM_A_MULTIFACETED_APPROACH_TO_INSCRIPTION_ANALYSIS](https://www.researchgate.net/publication/333017139_Combining_RTI_SFM_A_Multi-Faceted_approach_to_Inscription_Analysis_COMBINING_RTI_SFM_A_MULTIFACETED_APPROACH_TO_INSCRIPTION_ANALYSIS)

Castellano A., M. Martini, E. Sibilìa (2007) *Elementi di archeometria. Metodi fisici per i beni culturali*. Milano: Egea.

Cultural Heritage Imaging. (2011) *Reflectance Transformation Imaging: Guide to Highlight Image Processing* v1.4

Finanziato
dall'Unione europea
NextGenerationEU

Associated project to RESILIENCE

http://culturalheritageimaging.org/What_We_Offer/Downloads/rtibuilder/RTI_hlt_Processing_Guide_v14_beta.pdf

Cultural Heritage Imaging. (2013a) *Guide to RTI Viewer v 1.1*

http://culturalheritageimaging.org/What_We_Offer/Downloads/rtiviewer/RTIViewer_Guide_v1_1.pdf

Cultural Heritage Imaging. (2013b) *Reflectance Transformation Imaging: Guide to Highlight Capture* v2.0

http://culturalheritageimaging.org/What_We_Offer/Downloads/RTI_Hlt_Capture_Guide_v2_0.pdf

Cultural Heritage Imaging. (2014) *Reflectance Transformation Imaging. Glossary of Photographic and Technical Terms for RTI*

http://culturalheritageimaging.org/What_We_Offer/Downloads/Capture/CHI-RTI-Glossary_v1.pdf

Condorelli F. (2022) La documentazione del patrimonio culturale perduto mediante fotogrammetria e intelligenza artificiale. *MIMESIS.jsad. Journal of Science of Architectural Drawing*. <https://doi.org/10.56205/mim.2-1.5>

D'Andrea A., Ferrandino G., (2025) Decoding the Sacred: Challenges in Cataloguing and Integrating Digital Archives of Magical-Religious Artefacts from the Nile Valley and Beyond, in Melloni A., Cadeddu F., *The Digital Turn in Religious Studies. Research, Services, Infrastructures*, V&R Unipress, 325-348

D'Itria E. (2023) Kerma Amulets: Iconography and Manufacture Techniques. *Kush* 20. Proceedings of the 14th International Conference for Nubian Studies, 165-181.

Diara F. (2024) Data Extraction from 3D Scanning: Post-processing Filtering from Analytic and Informative Models of Small Archaeological Finds. *Archeologia e Calcolatori* 35.2, 225-234. <https://doi.org/10.19282/ac.35.2.2024.24>

Diara F., F.G. Barsacchi, S. de Martino (2024) Moving beyond the Content: 3D Scanning and Post-Processing Analysis of the Cuneiform Tablets of the Turin Collection. *Applied Sciences* 2024. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app14114492>.

Felicetti, A., Scarselli, T., Mancinelli, M. L., & Niccolucci, F. (2013) Mapping ICCD archaeological data to CIDOC-CRM: the RA Schema. In *CRMEX@ TPD* (pp. 11-22).

Giunta R. (2018) *The Aron Collection I. Islamic Magic-therapeutic Bowls*. Roma: Istituto per l'Oriente C.A. Nallino.

Associated project to RESILIENCE

Murano F., Felicetti A. (2023) *EpiDoc to CIDOC CRM Alignment. Towards a Semantic Integration of Epigraphic Information*. [10.5281/zenodo.7876524]

Remondino F. (2014) Photogrammetry: Theory, in F. Remondino and S. Campana (eds.), *3D Recording and Modelling in Archaeology and Cultural Heritage - Theory and Best Practices*. BAR International Series 2598. Oxford: Archaeopress, 65-73.

Remondino F., S. Campana (2014) *3D Recording and Modelling in Archaeology and Cultural Heritage - Theory and Best Practices*. BAR International Series 2598. Oxford: Archaeopress.

Surmen H.K. (2025) Reconstruction of Metal Objects - 3D Photogrammetry and Clay Coating. *Black Sea Journal of Engineering and Science* 8/2, 1-10. <https://doi.org/10.34248/bsengineering.1605086>.

Wood R.K.L. (2018) The Khosro Cup Replication Project: 3D imaging for a temporary exhibition, in K. Kelley and R.K.L. Wood (eds.) *Digital Imaging of Artifacts: Developments in Methods and Aims*. Oxford: Archaeopress, 165-182.

Selected Web Resources

<https://dasi.cnr.it>

<https://www.ilc.cnr.it/progetti/itant/>

<https://iconclass.org/>

<https://vcg.isti.cnr.it/relight/#download>

<https://www.blender.org/download/>

<https://sketchfab.com>

<https://www.capturingreality.com/>

<https://www.agisoft.com/>

<https://dev.epicgames.com/community/realityscan/learning>

1 Annexes

```
2 <?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"?>
3 <?xml-model href="https://epidoc.stoa.org/schema/9.4/tei-epidoc.rng"
4 schematypens="http://relaxng.org/ns/structure/1.0"?>
5 <?xml-model href="https://epidoc.stoa.org/schema/9.4/tei-epidoc.rng"
6 schematypens="http://purl.oclc.org/dsdl/schematron"?>
7 <TEI xmlns="http://www.tei-c.org/ns/1.0" xml:space="preserve" xml:lang="en">
8   <teiHeader>
9     <fileDesc>
10       <titleStmt>
11         <title>Inscription of <persName
12 role="queen">Amanishakheto</persName></title>
13       </titleStmt>
14       <editionStmt>
15         <edition>
16           <idno>REM 1294</idno>
17         </edition>
18         <editor role="compiler"><persName>Gilda Ferrandino</persName></editor>
19       </editionStmt>
20       <publicationStmt>
21         <authority></authority>
22         <date>2025</date>
23         <idno type="filename"></idno>
24         <availability>
25           <licence target="https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-
26 sa/4.0/">Creative Commons Attributions-NonCommercial-ShareAlike 4.0 International
27 License</licence>
28         </availability>
29       </publicationStmt>
30       <sourceDesc>
31         <msDesc>
32           <msIdentifier>
33             <country>Sudan</country>
34             <settlement
35 ref="https://www.geonames.org/379252">Khartoum</settlement>
36             <institution ana="https://sudannationalmuseum.com/">Sudan
37 National Museum</institution>
38             <repository>Sudan National Museum</repository>
39             <idno type="SNM">313338</idno>
40             <altIdentifier>
41               <idno type="REM">1294</idno>
42             </altIdentifier>
43           </msIdentifier>
44           <msContents>
45             <summary>royal inscription of the queen
46 Amanishakheto</summary>
47           </msContents>
48         </msDesc>
49       </sourceDesc>
50     </fileDesc>
51   </teiHeader>
52 </TEI>
```


Associated project to RESILIENCE

```
43                                     </msItem>
44                                     </msContents>
45                                     <physDesc>
46                                     <objectDesc>
47                                     <supportDesc>
48                                     <support>
49                                     <objectType
49 ana="http://vocab.getty.edu/page/aat/300007023">stela</objectType>
50                                     <material
50 ana="http://vocab.getty.edu/page/aat/300011376">sandstone</material>
51                                     <dimensions type="objectDimensions" unit="cm"
51 precision="high">
52                                     <height quantity="26.5">26.5</height>
53                                     <width quantity="13">13</width>
54                                     <depth quantity="3">3</depth>
55                                     </dimensions>
56                                     <rs type="reuse">probably reuse</rs>
57                                     <p>Small stela with rounded upper end,
57 characterized by two faces. The first is entirely occupied by a figurative
57 representation, the second corresponds to the epigraphic field that extends also on
57 the two edges of the stela.</p>
58                                     </support>
59                                     <condition>well preserved
60                                     <note>except for the central part of the back and
60 the two sides, where in several points the surface is abraded making it difficult to
60 read some signs</note>
61                                     </condition>
62                                     </supportDesc>
63                                     <layoutDesc>
64                                     <layout n="Recto">
65                                     <rs type="execution"
65 ana="http://vocab.getty.edu/page/aat/300404794">engraved</rs>
66                                     <rs type="script" source="https://wikis.hu-
66 berlin.de/teiegyptology/Thesauri:Languages_and_scripts#cite_ref-iana_org_3-0">Meroitic
66 Hieroglyphs</rs>
67                                     <note>on the recto of the stela there are two
67 cartouches with the name of goddess and queen</note>
68                                     </layout>
69                                     <layout n="Body">
70                                     <rs type="execution"
70 ana="http://vocab.getty.edu/page/aat/300404794">engraved</rs>
71                                     <rs type="script" source="https://wikis.hu-
71 berlin.de/teiegyptology/Thesauri:Languages_and_scripts#cite_ref-iana_org_3-0">Meroitic
71 cursive</rs>
72                                     <note>Continuous text on three faces: 15 lines per
72 face, with consecutive numbering proceeding from face A to face B to face C
72 </note>
73                                     </layout>
74                                     </layoutDesc>
75                                     </objectDesc>
76                                     <handDesc>
```


Associated project to RESILIENCE

```

77                                     <handNote>
78                                     <note type="paeographicNotes">the text is dated at the
Transitional A</note><height>letter-heights</height>
79                                     </handNote>
80                                     </handDesc>
81                                     <scriptDesc>
82                                     <scriptNote>
83                                     <rs type="writingsystem"
subtype="alphasyllabic">Meroitic hieroglyphs and cursive</rs>
84                                     <rs type="wordDivision">vertical double dots</rs>
85                                     </scriptNote>
86                                     </scriptDesc>
87                                     <decoDesc>
88                                     <p>On the upper part of the recto of the stele, there is a
winged solar disk flanked by two uraei. The wings occupy the entire lunette. At the
center, below the solar disk, the name of the sovereign, Amanishakheto, is carved in
hieroglyphics, while along the left side another inscription identifies the name of
the deity represented, Amesemi. The scene depicts the goddess embracing the queen,
holding her head with one hand, while with her left hand she lifts her elbow. A series
of ankh symbols pass from the deity's nose to that of the queen. The goddess wears a
long tunic decorated with stripes and dots, a fringed shawl tied around her. Her face
is characterized by traditional scarification marks, while her headdress consists of a
diadem with uraeus, two ribbons and a superstructure with the figure of a bird and
disk, resting on a boat-shaped element. The queen, characterized by a corpulent body,
wears a long pleated tunic and a shawl. She holds a scepter with her right hand while
raising her left toward the goddess as a sign of respect. Her hands are characterized
by long fingernails. Regarding the headdress, the queen wears a simple diadem without
uraei and superstructures; just above her hair, small dots can be seen following the
silhouette of her head. The scene represents the "choice" of Amanishakheto by the
goddess. The particularity of the representation is given by the simple diadem worn by
the queen, just like a prince.
89                                     </p>
90                                     </decoDesc>
91                                     </physDesc>
92                                     <history>
93                                     <origin>
94                                     <origPlace>
95                                     <placeName type="ancient"
ref="https://pleiades.stoa.org/places/795866">Naqa</placeName>
96                                     <placeName type="modern"
ref="https://www.geonames.org/9204033">Naqa</placeName>
97                                     </origPlace>
98                                     <origDate period="meroitic" notBefore="-0050" notAfter="-0001"
precision="low">1st century BCE</origDate>
99                                     </origin>
100                                    <provenance type="found" subtype="discovered" when="1999">
101                                    <placeName type="ancient"
ref="https://pleiades.stoa.org/places/795866">Naqa</placeName>
102                                    <placeName type="modern"
ref="https://www.geonames.org/9204033">Naqa</placeName>

```


Associated project to RESILIENCE

```
103                                     <placeName
type="detailed">found in the hypostyle hall of the Amun temple at Naqa, dated to the
period of the rulers Natakamani and Amanitore, during the archaeological campaign of
Naqa-Project</placeName>
104                                     </provenance>
105                                     <provenance type="observed">Modern location(s) (if different
from repository, above)
106                                     </provenance>
107                                     </history>
108                                     </msDesc>
109                                     </sourceDesc>
110                                     </fileDesc>
111                                     <profileDesc>
112                                     <langUsage>
113                                     <language ident="xmr" source="https://iso639-
3.sil.org/code/xmr">Meroitic</language>
114                                     </langUsage>
115                                     <textClass>
116                                     <keywords>
117                                     <term>stele</term>
118                                     <term>royal inscription</term>
119                                     <term>Amanishakheto</term>
120                                     <term>Amesemi</term>
121                                     </keywords>
122                                     </textClass>
123                                     </profileDesc>
124                                     <revisionDesc>
125                                     <change when="2025-04-11" who="Gilda Ferrandino">added</change>
126                                     </revisionDesc>
127 </teiHeader>
128
129 <text>
130   <body>
131     <div type="textpart" subtype="face" n="Recto">
132       <div type="textpart" subtype="cartouche" n="1" xml:lang="xmr" style="text-
direction:up-to-down">
133         <ab>
134           <lb n="1"/><persName role="queen">amnixeto</persName>qo
135         </ab>
136       </div>
137       <div type="textpart" subtype="cartouche" n="2" xml:lang="xmr" style="text-
direction:up-to-down">
138         <ab>
139           <lb n="1"/><persName role="goddess">amesemi</persName>qo
140         </ab>
141       </div>
142     </div>
143     <!-- Testo continuo -->
144   <div type="textpart" subtype="body">
```


Associated project to RESILIENCE

```

145          <!-- testo completo con segmentazione-->
146          <ab>
147              <lb n="1"/><seg type="face" n="A">am</seg><seg type="face" n="B">nixetoqo :
148              qo</seg><seg type="face" n="C">ro : k</seg>
149          <lb n="2"/><seg type="face" n="A">tke</seg><seg type="face" n="B">lo : menekeli :
150          mlo</seg><seg type="face" n="C">lo : m</seg>
151          <lb n="3"/><seg type="face" n="A">km</seg><seg type="face" n="B">kselo :
152          aritene</seg><seg type="face" n="C"> qrne</seg>
153          <lb n="4"/><seg type="face" n="A">lo : n</seg><seg type="face" n="B">k : armil :
154          tdxeso</seg><seg type="face" n="C"> noq</seg>
155          <lb n="5"/><seg type="face" n="A">ape</seg><seg type="face" n="B">selinote : qen :
156          no</seg><seg type="face" n="C">titk</seg>
157          <lb n="6"/><seg type="face" n="A">to : no</seg><seg type="face" n="B">tewi : etnkto :
158          nk :</seg><seg type="face" n="C"> ato :</seg>
159          <lb n="7"/><seg type="face" n="A">peno</seg><seg type="face" n="B">te : kek : qenħnok
160          :</seg><seg type="face" n="C"> ak :</seg>
161          <lb n="8"/><seg type="face" n="A">aso</seg><seg type="face" n="B">be[ca.3]q̄m̄ne` :
162          shr</seg><seg type="face" n="C">tel :</seg>
163          <lb n="9"/><seg type="face" n="A">xę : w</seg><seg type="face" n="B">k. : meter : tlk
164          : pl</seg><seg type="face" n="C">te :</seg>
165          <lb n="10"/><seg type="face" n="A">neṭe :</seg><seg type="face" n="B"> `se`mlolw :
166          apote : t</seg><seg type="face" n="C">mey</seg>
167          <lb n="11"/><seg type="face" n="A">se : y</seg><seg type="face" n="B">h : meterli [:]
168          k[ca.2]ll</seg><seg type="face" n="C">w : q̄e`</seg>
169          <lb n="12"/><seg type="face" n="A">lol.</seg><seg type="face" n="B">w : qketd :
170          netesem</seg><seg type="face" n="C">lo : e</seg>
171          <lb n="13"/><seg type="face" n="A">deḷi</seg><seg type="face" n="B">sey : tep : yxrt :
172          qo</seg><seg type="face" n="C">noḡ</seg>
173          <lb n="14"/><seg type="face" n="A">ld :</seg><seg type="face" n="B"> ketd : atewlitik
174          :</seg><seg type="face" n="C"> aso</seg>
175          <lb n="15"/><seg type="face" n="A">be : m</seg><seg type="face" n="B">rdi : tktoke :
176          esbo</seg><seg type="face" n="C">ħt</seg>
177          </ab>
178          </div>
179          <div type="apparatus">
180              <p>external apparatus criticus (if applicable)</p>
181          </div>
182          <div type="translation">
183              <p>translation(s)</p>
184          </div>
185          <div type="commentary">
186              <p>commentary</p>
187          </div>
188          <div type="bibliography">
189              <p>bibliography of previous editions, discussion, etc.</p>
190          </div>
191          </body>
192          </text>
193          <facsimile>

```


Associated project to RESILIENCE

```
180          <surface>
181          <desc>Recto of the stele</desc>
182          <graphic n="1" url="REM1294_Amanishakheto_Naqa/_DSC0071.jpg" resp="Gilda
Ferrandino">
183          <desc>Photograph for epigraphic studies taken on <date
when="20121101">2012</date></desc>
184          </graphic>
185          </surface>
186
187    </facsimile>
188 </TEI>
189
```

(End of Document)